

Opening up Education in South Mediterranean Countries

OpenMed Project

External Evaluation Final

Report

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Opening up Education in South Mediterranean Countries

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About OpenMed

The overarching goal of OpenMed is to raise awareness and facilitate the adoption of Open Educational Resources (OER) and Open Educational Practices (OEP) in the South Mediterranean region, with a particular focus on Egypt, Jordan, Morocco and Palestine.

OpenMed fosters the role of universities as knowledge providers not only to their on-campus students but also beyond the walls of institutions, especially towards disadvantaged groups (e.g. low-income peoples, disabled students, people living in rural areas, learners at risk of low achievement, refugees).

Members of the Consortium

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- [EDEN, European Distance and E-Learning Network, UK](#)

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Executive Summary

The OpenMed project has come to an end, after three years of work, the project has produced a series tangible and intangible benefits, as this project aimed at building capacities and raising awareness Open Education at regional, institutional and personal, towards having an impact on professional development and at policy level.

This report provides feedback about OpenMed activities with regards of its impact on the HE Sector, at institutional level, at individual level, on the society as a whole, and on the OE global community. Also, this report addresses the sustainability / exploitation of results, including aspects related to conference presentations, research papers, blogposts, dissemination events and networks and communities.

This report addresses the quality of the outcomes by analysing them in terms of its impact, aligned with the mid and long-term needs of the project key target stakeholders. The quality criteria used to assess the outcomes of the project are usability, flexibility, extensibility and transferability and the quality principles used to evaluate the results are flexibility, participation, efficacy and effectiveness, innovation, coherence, transparency and relevance.

Finally, a series of recommendations are provided to the partners and other stakeholders in order to ensure the sustainability of the project and more importantly, foster Open Educational Policies at institutional and national level.

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I. Impact of the project

1. Introduction

This report aims at providing a detailed analysis of the achievements of the OpenMed project, by assessing not only the outcomes but the processes used to identify the value this project has had across the Higher Education (HE) sector, on partner institutions, on the society as a whole, at individual level and furthermore, on the Open Education Global Community.

To understand the ways which the impact occurs, it is important to consider who has been directly affected by the project and who are the key stakeholders and beneficiaries of the project. Also, it is key to consider the current state of the arts in Open Education before and after the project by studying the baseline environment and the needs of the partners to enable Open Educational Practices in their countries, as this is where the key drivers and barriers are identified and also, where the key enablers can be understood.

Open Education in the MENA region was initiated through the adoption of digital learning practices. The first mention to the need of opening up education in the MENA region appears in the report *The Road Not Traveled Education Reform in the Middle East and North Africa* by the World Bank (2008)¹ in which is stated that in regards with the political accountability and education outcomes as the importance of public accountability for better delivery of social services is associated with open societies, greater transparency, and opportunities for contestability.

As mentioned in Baporikar (2014)² in the *Handbook of Research on Higher Education in the MENA Region*, the MENA region lacks school resources and operational mechanisms that can facilitate fulfilling educational goals. Making available open or supported educational resources, and coordination between curricular objectives,

¹ World Bank (2008). *The road not traveled: Education reform in the Middle East and North Africa*. Retrieved from http://siteresources.worldbank.org/INTMENA/Resources/EDU_Flagship_Full_ENG.pdf

² Baporikar, N. (Ed.). (2014). *Handbook of Research on Higher Education in the MENA Region: Policy and Practice*. IGI Global. Retrieved from https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=KKB_BAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR1&dq=Handbook+of+Research+on+Higher+Education+in+the+MENA+Region&ots=awZkW9PecT&sig=MV6FHmfo83yDYXRAmTgmoEbvNEc#v=onepage&q=Handbook%20of%20Research%20on%20Higher%20Education%20in%20the%20MENA%20Region&f=false

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mechanisms used by teachers and appropriate selection of assessment material can convey a functional and manageable educational system.

Also, as reported by the African Development Bank (2015)³, MOOCs are a tool to fundamentally change the educational system in the MENA region, as these can leverage the trend to transform the classroom experience by establishing open education environments and setting up open learning networks for teachers.

An enabler for Open Education in the MENA region is the large HE enrolment, which is above 30% of the population aged 18-24, which is high compared to other regions, which has led to over-crowdedness of the learning spaces, therefore, HE systems are seeking expand the means to foster learning through, for example, blended learning and Open University programmes, by developing e-learning and distance education programmes⁴. As it can be seen in the EACEA (2017) reports *Overview of the Higher Education System*⁵ published by the European Commission on Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency, in which the current state of the HE systems from [Morocco](#), [Egypt](#), [Jordan](#) and [Palestine](#) are described in detail, the MENA region can enhance their educational delivery by adopting Open Educational Practices as these can help institutions, educators to support their learners and their educational communities.

The mission of OpenMed has been to enable and catalyse Open Educational Practices in the MENA, considering the socio-political context and challenges of the partner countries, towards ensuring that the adoption of such practices can fulfil their educational needs.

2. Impact on the HE Sector

The OpenMed project aimed at enabling Open Education by fostering good practices in use, creation, and adoption of Open Educational Resources, and to achieve its goals, a series of activities and strategies were used, in order to support the project partners to

³ African Development Bank (2015). Fundamentally changing the way we educate students in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region. Retrieved from https://www.afdb.org/fileadmin/uploads/afdb/Documents/Publications/North_Africa_-_Working_paper_-_Fundamentally_changing_the_way_we_educate_students_in_the_Middle_East_and_North_Africa_MENA_region.pdf

⁴ European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education. Retrieved from <https://enqa.eu/index.php/enqa-qa-project-in-the-mena-region/>

⁵ EACEA (2017) reports *Overview of the Higher Education System*. European Commission on Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/erasmus-plus/library/overview-higher-education-system-in-partner-countries-regions-1234-and-7_en

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define their priorities and to design their agendas according with their own needs, supported by strategic guidelines developed for and by the project stakeholders, such as the [OER Regional Agenda for the South-Mediterranean Universities](#) and the set of recommendations to institutional leaders and policy makers.

A key catalyser were the [OER National Strategy Forums](#) conducted in [Egypt](#) (November 2016), [Morocco](#) (December 2016), [Jordan](#) (February 2017), [Palestine](#) (April 2017), and [Morocco](#) (January 2018), as these acted as arenas to foster strategic discussions to enable the pathway towards policy making, as senior managements and educators share a table in which Open Education projects were showcased alongside with the institutional agendas and roadmaps, leading to foster strategies to enable Open Education at partners universities, and also, inspiring others, as guests from neighbouring universities were also invited to participate, in order to widening up the participation in HEIs stakeholders in the region.

The project has had an impact in the regional HE sector, not only at partners and country level, but it has extended to nearby countries due to the wide participation of the national forums, however, at policy level, two of the partner countries, Morocco and Palestine, have had an impact in their national policies or in their national agendas.

In Morocco, the OpenMed Partners, led by Dr Khalid Berrada (Cadi Ayyad University) and Dr Ahmed Almakari (Ibn Zohr University) had launched a [national declaration about Open Education in Morocco](#), which has been discussed at ministerial level, as it has the potential to influence on the development of a national education policy in the short term that fosters Open Education initiatives, as these are gaining space due to the adoption of such practices at the [Maroc Université Numérique](#), which has been launched in 2017 with the participation and contribution of the OpenMed partners, aiming at support the development of training programs taking full advantage of digital platforms by placing digit education at the heart of higher education, support the digital initiatives of institutions and promote the visibility of the Moroccan Universities and of their digital resources.

In the case of Palestine, Dr Saida Affouneh from An-Najah University has acted as advisor to the Government of Palestine in addressing Open Education within the current national policy. Also, partners from the German Jordanian University are leading on a national e-learning committee that has been requested directly by the Ministry of Education, an in this national committee their aim is to further promote Open Education across the other universities which are part of the national committee.

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The project, has also the potential to further contribute to national policies and regulations regarding open education, as the partners institutions are leading their national discussions regarding the importance of opening up and sharing teaching and learning resources and also, fostering good practices that can be showcased at national and international level through the Open Education Centres funded by the OpenMed project, for this reason, the project has designed a set of recommendations to support institutional leaders and policy-makers to strategically prioritise Open Education to further develop the education system in the South-Mediterranean.

The project has also contributed to the establishment of a sub-network for [Open Education and E-learning through UNIMED](#) which will support partner institutions in adopting good practices for Open and Digital education which can be shared inside and outside the network.

Also, the good practices showcased and developed throughout the project, such as the [Open Education Training Week in Torino](#), the training materials of the course [Open Education: fundamentals and approaches](#), the [9 learning circles](#), and the OER-related [projects](#), are leading elements that can contribute to foster excellence and innovation in teaching, encouraging the competitiveness of HEIs by engaging with students in a novel and participative manner promoting technology enhanced learning that can suit different learning and teaching styles.

The outcomes of the project, such as the [compendium](#) of good practices, the [capacity building course](#) and its [learning circles](#), alongside with the [innovation Centres for Open Education](#) are pioneer initiatives in the region, which can be further reused, expanded, adopted in other developing economies, as these provide not only academic information and good practices in teaching and learning but also, provide innovative methodologies for academic development and training and for content and curricular development.

Also, outcomes from the [OER National Strategy Forums](#) have provided to the communities from partner universities, and to the communities of the non-partners institutions inspirational and participative spaces where peer-learning is fostered towards exchanging good practices in Open Education which can be enhanced by welcoming contributions from educators from different institutions, thus paving the creation of national communities of practice.

Furthermore, the project outcomes can enhance and improve dynamics to further foster the creation of institutional and national policies, by involving a wide range of stakeholders in generating and documenting good teaching and learning practices in a participative manner.

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3. Impact at institutional level

With regards to extent of the project impact at institutional level, and according to the information gathered at the [Final OpenMed Conference in Rome](#), (October, 2018), it can be understood as follows by each partner institution:

German Jordanian University: The project has led to improve the e-learning infrastructure, towards enhancing the provision of digital content. Also, throughout the Open Education centre, the institution aim at building capacities within their faculty towards promoting the benefits of Open Education. Furthermore, to raise awareness of the benefits of Open Education, at GJU, training for senior management was conducted in order to gain their confidence to be able to implement their institutional roadmaps with the aim of fostering the development of comprehensive open policies that includes Open Education, Open Science and Open Access. Regarding the planned use of the [online course](#): GJU is trying to expand the use of OER in the educational process. In fact, there is a dedicated committee focused on expanding the use of e-learning and open education. So, it is proposed that faculty can start their open education journey by taking the OpenMed course. As we all know, the OpenMed course provides an organised and concentrated teaching materials about open education.

Princess Sumaya University: The partners recall their impact at starting a change of culture in their institution by being able to improve the learning support to over fifty thousand students, as by using the Open Education Centres to create OERs, they will be able not only to train their faculty but also to directly work with students to create OERs according with their needs.

Alexandria University: In order to foster Open Education across faculty level, the partners at Alexandria University are using the OpenMed learning circles methodology as their key approach to train academics in Open Education Practices and in the development of OERs through their Open Education centres. They are also producing tailor made resources to support their peers in developing OERs and also, in the digitisation of learning materials.

Cairo University: For the partners, the Open Education centres at their institution is the key element to foster Open Education as they are training faculty and learning technologist to create OERs that can be effectively used in their local context, as by being a large University with a large e-learning component, they are aiming at embedding a culture within their e-learning

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technologists to make open the default not the exception when talking about digital learning resources.

An-Najah University: The project has helped to raised their faculty self confidence in their own work, as their learning circle has created a community of practice that allows them to share expertise across the faculty widening up their participation on a scholar community, which has the support from the Dean of Education towards raising the understanding of Open Education at faculty and senior management level, in order to become able to support a large number of students through Open Education.

Birzeit University: At Birzeit University, the biggest impact of the project has been to become able to bridge excellence in teaching and learning with innovative methods for supporting their students learning, and to become a national reference centre for Open Education in the country by being able to disseminate knowledge not only at faculty level but also at national level.

Ibn Zohr University: For the partners at Ibn Zohr University the biggest impact is the learning their acquired about Open Education, which spirit is progressively being embedded across the faculty by fostering a continuation of the work conducted by the learning circles, but moreover, impact means to have been able to enable a national debate that may lead to policy or national agenda throughout collaboration and by sharing expertise and ideas with partners at universities in the country.

Cadi Ayyad University: Impact for Cadi Ayyad University, mean not only fostering a culture of Open Education within their own university, but also, embedding Open Education into the national agenda through the Moroccan Open Education Declaration which had led them to collaborate in a wide series of projects within the Maroc Université Numérique.

Also, for European partners, the project has had an impact at practice and policy level at their institutions through OpenMed, which can be seen as follows:

Coventry University: For the partners at Coventry University, the main impact has been the international collaboration and the opportunities to review diverse and excellent practices in teaching and learning, and also, the project has helped them to develop and implement an institutional policy for Open Education which is expected to be rolled out in the upcoming months in order to support the development of openly licensed content and embed a culture of openness inside the university.

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Politecnico di Torino: For them, the main impact through the project is the development of a set of principles for towards fostering Open Educational Practices and resources alongside with Open Access Papers and Open Science which has led to the creation of an institutional repository for open research outcomes and that included all the students dissertations. Also, they are developing guidelines towards recognising the work of their faculty in Open Access, Open Education and Open Science, and fostering community engagement with the community by opening up their conference materials.

Universidad Internacional de la Rioja: During the project, UNIR has launched their Open Education Policy, and they are now considering ways to refine its current teaching and learning resources, towards starting to create an integrated business plan for the university with strategic business partners that will help them to convince the managers about approaches to openness, human rights, access and, fostering the idea that openness can be profitable.

Universidad de Sevilla: For the partners at Universidad de Sevilla, the key impacts are related with being able to research and understand the benefits of Open Education, and the value of the development of partnerships to foster communities of practices. They are aiming at engaging students in producing knowledge through Open Educational Practices, and also, finding mechanisms to reward their faculty when they engage in the creation of OERs. Also, they have developed a strategic research line to engage in discourse analysis and participation in Open Education towards enabling good practices for teaching and learning in multicultural contexts.

UNIMED: According to Dr Marcello Scalisi, Director of UNIMED, The OpenMed project has created the conditions to foster Open Education and OER in the institutional agenda of UNIMED, as Open Education and OER have become one of the priorities of the UNIMED network. Since its initial development, as a Capacity Building project, awareness has been raised gradually, not only amongst the project partners, but also throughout the whole network, due of the importance of this subject not only from its educational value, but also from a political-institutional perspective. This has gained a more symbolic value in a troubled region like the Mediterranean, as Open Education and OER are a fundamental tool to foster the universal right to study, as it is now widely recognised by the members of UNIMED, and around which new energies and intelligences are being gathered. The resolution of conflicts and tensions in the Mediterranean region depends on the democratisation of knowledge and therefore relies on Open Education and OER. Thus, UNIMED will be promoting

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a strategic policy on Open Education and OER for the Mediterranean which has been made possible thanks to the OpenMED project.

In general, the benefits for the partner Universities are not limited to the time of the project, but these go beyond it, having the potential to have an impact at widening up the participation and the access to higher education, at fostering spaces to build capacities for the educators not only at institutional level, but expanding their training network across the country and the region, but more importantly, the learnings and outcomes of the projects can have an impact in fostering policies at institutional and international level.

4. Impact at individual level

In numbers, those who attended the [Open Education Training Week in Torino](#) and the online course [Open Education: fundamentals and approaches](#), can be seen as follows (tables obtained from the [Course Review Report](#)).

Event	Number of people	Respondents of the survey	Learners	Facilitators	Total
Torino Week	60	43	39	8	47
Online course	74	60	49	11	60

Table 1: Participants in the OpenMed trainings

The attendance distribution for the [Open Education Training Week in Torino](#) can be seen in the table below:

Did you attend the Torino Week			
Country	Yes	No	Total
Egypt	26.67%	0.00%	26.67%
Jordan	18.33%	1.67%	20.00%
Lebanon	2.13%	76.92%	18.33%
Morocco	19.15%	7.69%	16.67%
Palestine	21.28%	7.69%	18.33%
Total	78.33%	21.67%	100.00%

Table 2: Attendance by country

The competences acquired during the [Open Education Training Week in Torino](#), both by learners and facilitators are described in the table below:

Torino week- Competences and new learning gained Facilitators and Learners		
University	Good	Excellent
An Najah National University	50.00%	37.50%
Alexandria University	42.86%	57.14%
Birzeit University	100.00%	0.00%
Cairo University	75.00%	25.00%
German Jordanian University	33.33%	66.67%
Ibn Zohr University	50.00%	50.00%
Notre Dame University	9.09%	0.00%
Princess Sumaya University	37.50%	50.00%
Minia University	0.00%	100.00%
AL-Ahlyya Amman University	0.00%	100.00%
Cadi Ayyad University	50.00%	0.00%

Table 3: Torino week- Competences and new learning gained

The role of the people involved in the course [Open Education: fundamentals and approaches](#), can be seen distributed as follows:

Role in the OpenMed Course		
Country	Facilitator	Participant
Egypt	18.75%	81.25%
Jordan	25.00%	75.00%
Lebanon	9.09%	90.91%
Morocco	20.00%	80.00%
Palestine	18.18%	81.82%

Table 4: Role in the OpenMed Course

The evaluation of different aspects of the course [Open Education: fundamentals and approaches](#) given by the course participants can be seen distributed as follows:

Course evaluation – participants	Very Poor	Poor	Average	Good	Excellent
Overall structure of the course	0.00%	0.00%	4.08%	57.14%	36.73%
Length of the course	0.00%	2.04%	24.49%	48.98%	22.45%
Clarity of the language	0.00%	2.04%	2.04%	51.02%	42.86%
Platform and navigation	0.00%	2.04%	2.04%	51.02%	42.86%
Balance between multimedia and text	0.00%	2.04%	20.41%	38.78%	36.73%
Level of support from the facilitators	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	48.98%	48.98%
Effectiveness of the learning circles	0.00%	0.00%	2.04%	55.10%	40.82%
Overall group collaboration	0.00%	0.00%	6.12%	48.98%	42.86%

Table 5: evaluation of the course

Finally, to measure the impact of the learners and facilitators of the [Open Education Training Week in Torino](#) (September 2017) and [Open Education: fundamentals and approaches](#) course (October 2017 – March 2018), [9 learning circles](#) and OER-related [projects](#), they were asked if whether they felt more confident after participating in the capacity building stages of the course, they were asked how confident they were before and after the course in the following criteria:

- Open Educational Practices [OEP] - Open Pedagogies
- Open Licensing
- MOOCs
- OER production and use
- Open Education in general

Before the course, the participants' self perception and confidence bounced between not confident at all to mildly confident (see graphs below [from [Course Review Report](#)])

Figure 1: Confidence pre course

However, after the course, the participants declared to feel mostly confident or very confident as can be seen below

Figure 2: Confidence post course

The capacity building package, which included the [Open Education Training Week in Torino](#) (September 2017) and [Open Education: fundamentals and approaches](#) course (October 2017 – March 2018), [9 learning circles](#), OER-related [projects](#) fostered and developed skills in open education but also, it raised the confidence of the participants, which means that it has had an impact at individual level (for further information see, the [Course Review Report](#))

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5. Impact on the society as a whole

To assess the impact of the project on the society, the impact is described under a series of criteria presented below:

Potential of the project to pay particular attention to least developed countries: The OpenMed project has paid attention to the local needs of the region, carefully localising the materials and resources produced in order to foster local communities and expand the impact outside of the partner universities, involving other local stakeholders from neighbouring developing economies.

Potential of the project to engage Partner Countries HEIs in new means of cooperation with employers and other stakeholders (e.g. NGOs, associations, etc.): During the course of the project, and through the national forums, an open door approach was used in order to invite educators and senior management from other universities in the country and in the region, fostering engagement and peer-exchange with other stakeholders.

Measures contributing to improving lifelong learning approaches in the Partner Country HEIs: OpenMed key outcome is a capacity building course in Open Education, which can be adopted, adapted and localised by any institution in the region. Also, OpenMed has developed a unique open learning methodology, called learning circles, which aims at facilitating peer-learning, and this methodology can be widely adopted by any interested stakeholder, and also, enable channels for peer-support from the OpenMed partners in the region.

6. Impact on the OE global community

The OpenMed project has had an impact not only in the South Mediterranean region, but further on, in the global Open Education Community. The partners presented at several international conferences, including the [OER17](#) and [OER18](#) conference which is a global event for Open Education practitioners and advocates.

Also, as by having experts guests invited to get involved in the project, both in the [compendium](#), and in the [webinar series](#), the project was presented to the international community gaining attention for the community of practice of the [Open Education Working Group](#), from [Open Knowledge International](#), who followed their activities closely, helping to disseminate their activities. Also, the [Open Education Consortium](#) has engaged with the OpenMed activities during the [Open Education Week](#) and on the [Open Access Week](#), and partnering for the [Year Of Open](#), a global celebration of Open Education initiated by the Open Education Consortium in 2017, which brings together

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organisations and initiatives actively committed to participate and contribute to widen participation on Open Education. As well, [Creative Commons](#) have featured the [OER Morocco Declaration](#) and contributed to the project with two Webinars, [Open Education: The Moral, Business & Policy Case for OER](#) and [Open licensing in the Erasmus+ CBHE projects](#) and, the European Distance and E-learning network (EDEN) have [showcased the project](#).

Also, the [OER world map](#) has listed OpenMed in its portal. Furthermore, [OER Africa](#) is promoting the [Open Education: fundamentals and approaches](#) in their [site](#), the [GO GN](#) network has hosted the [OpenMed Webinars](#) and [ROER4D](#) have [showcased OpenMed](#) as well as [OER Lebanon](#). Finally, other institutions, such as [Harvard University](#) and [Drexel University](#), have portrayed OpenMed. Also, world leaders and experts such as [Lorna Campbell](#), have written about OpenMed.

As it can be seen, the reach and impact of OpenMed has been global, raising awareness of the advancements of Open Education in the MENA region, gaining attention of media, as recorded in the [press-review section](#) of the project website. The project has been portrayed in large national newspapers, such as La Vanguardia in Spain, that published a report about the [facilitators meeting in Madrid](#) (2017), as well as the Spanish newspaper 20 Minutos that mentions the event at [UNIR](#), and Europa Press, that also [highlights the project](#). The key global Open Education organisations have engaged with the project and the partners acknowledging and recognising the importance of this project and the value of the community of practice fostered by OpenMed.

II. Evaluation of the main project outcomes

The main project outcomes have been assessed using a set of quality principles and quality criteria, which were used to build and develop these outcomes in order to ensure their quality.

According to the answers provided by the partners in the internal evaluation questionnaire, the outcomes/results which contributed or will contribute the most to the strategic priorities of their institution and to their modernisation and internationalisation strategies can be seen in figure 3 below.

Figure 3: Most relevant outcomes

According the partners, these outcomes/results are relevant to themselves and or for their institutions because, *these outcomes are very essential to guarantee sustainability of achieving project objectives and will help to create more educators*

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who are involved in open education and will eventually expand the pool of open education user and promoters.

The OpenMed outcomes will help in expanding the cooperation with policy makers in each country in the region. As these can be adopted easily as we are a network of universities and these outcomes can be transferred and circulated.

*In regards with the training and the development of communities of practice, the partners mentioned that **training and networking enabled our university to think more strategically about OEP and OER**, and that these **reinforce the existing potential in terms of openness of education and to implement this new culture among university professors and staff**. Furthermore, the course has help them **realising the OER Regional Agenda for our university and the region, which will be reproduced in our institution through the innovation Centre for Open Education.***

*Finally, for the partners, **the forums should be held every year to keep fostering open education despite the project being over**, in which the **policy recommendations can be discussed in upcoming forums to be adopted by the partners to develop institutional policies.***

1. Quality Criteria

All the project outcomes have been assessed using the four following criteria.

- **Usability**, the extent to which the project outcomes can be readily used by the intended target users;
- **Flexibility**, the extent to which the project outcomes can be adapted to changing needs /circumstances and to different geographical environments;
- **Extensibility**, the use of the outcomes in similar but different settings as piloted as part of the project (e.g. within the same type of institutions but with other learners);
- **Transferability**, referring to whether and how the project outcomes can be transferred to other target groups or other settings or countries other than the ones included in the OpenMed project.

The table below summarises the state of the project outcomes according with the quality criteria.

Outcome	Usability	Flexibility	Extensibility	Transferability
OpenMed compendium	X	X	X	X

Five OER National Strategy Forum	X	X	X	X
OER Regional Agenda for the South-Mediterranean Universities	X	X	X	X
A national declaration about Open Education in Morocco	X	X	X	X
8 innovation Centres for Open Education	X	X	X	X
Open Education Training Week in Torino and online training course	X	X	X	X
9 learning circles	X	X	X	X
Webinar series	X	X	X	X
OER-related projects	X	X	X	X
Training materials of the course Open Education: fundamentals and approaches	X	X	X	X
Pilot Course Evaluation Report	X	X	X	X
Active network of experts and educators	X	X	X	X
Set of recommendations to institutional leaders and policy makers	X	X	X	X

Table 6: Project outcomes according with the quality criteria.

The main outcomes over the three-year period assessed under the above-mentioned criteria can be seen as follows:

1. The [compendium](#) publication and its executive summaries in English, French, and Arabic with a review of Open Education globally and in particular the South-Mediterranean region with 11 case studies and a series of video interviews with experts in open education: The compendium, both as exercise and as resource is a great material, at **usability** level it can be re-edited, adapted, also its **flexibility** allows it to be contextualised and also **extended** from in its current form, and as per its form, it can become easily **transferred** to other contexts.
2. [Five OER National Strategy Forums](#) conducted in [Egypt](#) (November 2016), [Morocco](#) (December 2016), [Jordan](#) (February 2017), and [Palestine](#) (April 2017), plus Morocco (January 2018) have fostered the inclusivity and **usability** of the resources and activities developed for the projects. The forums format is

- flexible**, as it can be adapted to widening up participation and gather new actors engaging educators and senior management in Open Education, also, the forums can be **extended** to foster institutional that can be **transferred** to other universities and educational centres.
3. The [OER Regional Agenda for the South-Mediterranean Universities](#), is the starting point for the development of action plans and roadmaps at institutional level is a **usable** tool for the partners to develop institutional strategies that can be easily adopted by partners universities, as per being an **flexible** tool, it facilitates the adaptation and adoption of this guidelines, also, these can be **extended** to be adopted by non-partner institutions making this a **transferable** tool to foster policy-making
 4. The [national declaration about Open Education in Morocco](#) is a **usable** tool as it derives from the [Scottish Open Education Declaration](#) and it due to its **flexibility** it can be easily adopted to foster similar declarations in other countries, **extending** its potential to other areas such as Open Access and Open Science, facilitating the **transferability** of the declaration into other open domains and countries to foster effective policy making.
 5. [8 innovation Centres for Open Education](#) at South-Mediterranean partner universities where technical and networking infrastructure is available to university students, teachers and staff. Funding technology oriented centres that that support not only the development of OER but also capacity building, academic development and also to use the outcomes for further research about OEP can foster the **usability** of the materials produced by each centre, providing arenas to promote professional development in a **flexible** manner, widening up participation and **extending** the reach of the centres to foster research and good practices that can be **transferred** to other universities to enhance Open Educational Practices.
 6. 74 educators trained at the [Open Education Training Week in Torino](#) (September 2017) and [online](#) (October 2017 – March 2018) to adopt Open Education approaches. Starting a learning path through a face-to-face experience is the most **useful** way to engage learners from a wide diversity of countries and backgrounds in a **flexible** way, to foster a community of practices, **extending** the reach of the network, as the educators' network aims at inspiring other by exchanging and **transferring** knowledge to other educators and to their learners.
 7. [9 learning circles](#) in Egypt, Morocco, Palestine, Jordan and Lebanon facilitated by a network of 15 local facilitators. The learning circles are an **useful** and innovative methodology to foster peer-learning and to build communities of practices and a network of champions inside institutions. This methodology can

- promote **flexible** learning, extending its reach outside the learning materials, by engaging the learners in learning from each other towards transferring their knowledge inside and outside their learning circles.
8. The [webinar series](#) on different aspects of Open Education, with international leaders in the field. These Webinars were a mean to connect experts with learners in order to foster a wider engagement with the global community of OE practitioners and advocates. The Webinars are **useful**, as supported the community of practice but also, due to its **flexible** nature, the videos were reused as complementary materials in the validated version of the course, **extending** the availability of materials and resources for upcoming learners, facilitating the **transferability** of knowledge between experts and learners after the end of the project.
 9. A variety of OER-related [projects](#) created by participants in the course. The results of the learning of the participants are a **useful** way to create OER. The **flexible** nature of the projects, allows the projects to be adopted and **extended** as these can be **transferred** to other groups of learners in upcoming editions of the course.
 10. The training materials of the course [Open Education: fundamentals and approaches](#), is composed by 5 modules, activities, and project works steps, publicly available in English, French, and Arabic. The course content has been designed to ensure its usability across a wide range of learners, and its flexible design allows the content to be used as a whole package or as standalone units can be reused, adapted, **extended**, contextualised and **transferred** in order to support academic development programmes not only at partner level but also, at international level, as these can be widely adopted by Universities globally.
 11. A [Pilot Course Evaluation Report](#), with recommendations and suggestions for improving and enhancing future editions of the course. The pilot course was evaluated using a open-peer review approach in which the external evaluator worked directly with the authors to provide them with feedback, which was also complements from the review of the opinions of the learners and from the authors in a **useful** and direct manner, in order to support the partners in improving the course, asking them to exchange content between modules due to its **flexible** nature, **extending** and improving these to enhance its quality. One of the most valuable elements is the methodology of the report, as open-peer-review can be **transferred** into any other assessment in similar projects.
 12. The active network of experts and educators interested in promoting open education. Fostering a community of practice was one of the key objectives of this project, as a network is **useful** to enhance and achieve the aims of opening up education and so far is one of the most accomplished outcomes, however,

to foster and widening up the community, the UNIMED sub-network is key to keep this community active, by providing a **flexible** arena to engage and participate, **extending** the network beyond OpenMed and using the sub-network as a platform to **transfer** knowledge across their partner institutions.

13. The [set of recommendations](#) to institutional leaders and policy makers to strategically prioritise Open Education to further develop the education system in the South-Mediterranean. These recommendations are **useful** to enable the development of policies at institutional level in a **flexible** and contextualised ways, and also to support the implementation of the roadmaps, to **extend** and strengthen the possibilities of engage senior management in fostering national policies and **transferring** their policy knowledge to foster policies across the region.

2. Quality principles

Also, the outcomes were reviewed against the following principles.

- **Participation:** All partners take part in all project meetings and events related to the tasks or activities they have to carry out. All decisions taken together with the operational specifications of the activities are recorded in written form.
- **Documentation:** The working documents and operational specifications of the activities are written and stored to facilitate project review and management.
- **Efficacy and Effectiveness:** The processes/phases produce the expected results in terms of planned outputs in the timeframe foreseen and within the remit of working plan. The corrective measures are agreed and approved by all partners. The level of the resources employed for carrying out the activities is coherent with the resource level anticipated in the approved project. All corrective measures are approved by all partners
- **Innovation:** The value commitment of the partners and stakeholders supports innovation
- **Coherence:** The processes/phases produce the expected results in terms of planned outputs
- **Transparency:** The nature and level of resourcing available and all processes are transparent to all members of the partnership
- **Relevance:** Relevance of the processes and results/outcomes is validated periodically. If necessary corrective measures are put in place

A summary of the review of the outcomes can be seen in the table below:

Outcome	Participation	Documentation	Efficacy and Effectiveness	Innovation	Coherence	Transparency	Relevance
OpenMed compendium	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Five OER National Strategy Forum	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
OER Regional Agenda for the South-Mediterranean Universities	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
A national declaration about Open Education in Morocco	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
8 innovation Centres for Open Education	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Open Education Training Week in Torino and online training course	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
9 learning circles	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Webinar series	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
OER-related	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

projects							
Training materials of the course "Open Education: fundamentals and approaches	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Pilot Course Evaluation Report	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Active network of experts and educators	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Set of recommendations to institutional leaders and policy makers	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Table 7: Outcomes reviewed against the following principles

In detail, the analysis of the outcomes against the quality principles of the project can be seen as follows:

1. In regards with the [compendium](#), it has been made in a **participatory** manner, involving a series of stakeholders in each of its stages, including its revision and translation, which were made using an open peer-review approach. The process **documentation** was made available for consultation and all the partners were timely informed about the process of the book. Regarding the **efficacy and effectiveness** of the compendium, this was designed in order to facilitate learning and to comprehend good practices in OE that can inspire learners and practitioners. The compendium is **innovative**, as it gathers practices from the MENA region and from European partners and experts, and its content can be adapted, updated, reused and extended by any interested party in the OE community to develop capacities amongst educators and students. Also, the compendium is **coherent** with the principles of OE, as it fosters collaboration, openness, **transparency** of the processes and creativity in

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order to achieve a resource that can be used as key component of learning paths. Finally, the compendium is **relevant** for the global OE community, as a good source of information for researchers about the MENA region and other OE advancements at international level, alongside with showcasing exemplary practices that can be adopted in emerging economies.

2. Regarding the [OER National Strategy Forums](#) conducted in [Egypt](#) (November 2016), [Morocco](#) (December 2016), [Jordan](#) (February 2017), and [Palestine](#) (April 2017), plus Morocco (January 2018), all of these have been designed to act as **participatory** arenas which hosted partners and non partner educators in exchanging good practices. The **documentation** of the forums has been designed in order to guarantee that all the participants have access to the agendas and the presentations, and also, after each forum, a [report](#) has been provide to each one of the hosting partners in order to give them with recommendations for future editions. The forums have been **efficient**, as these have achieved their objectives of sharing good practices across their communities of practice and beyond their institution, and also, these have been **effective**, as these have led the path to establish a series of good practices to support the activities of the OE centres and to start developing policies and strategic plans for the universities. Also, the forums have been great spaces to foster **innovation**, as the exchange of practices have provided to the participants with ideas to foster OE in the classroom. The forums have been coherent with the strategic aims of the project, as it fostered the discussions to enable the delivering the project in a proactive and **transparent** way, therefore, its **relevance** can be understood as being the key enablers to foster good practices at institutional and regional level.
3. The [OER Regional Agenda for the South-Mediterranean Universities](#), has been developed collaboratively, fostering the **participation** from partners and other key stakeholders, such as OE experts. The agenda and its development process have been widely **documented** and shared across the partners to gather their perspectives, also, in order to provide access to the discussion to the agenda in an **efficient** and **effective** manner, it was made [open for comments](#), using an innovative approach, publishing it in way in which anyone could co-create it, in **coherence** with the open spirit of the project, so stakeholders and the OE could contribute to it in a **transparent** manner, towards ensuring the **relevance** of the agenda across the OE policy landscape.
4. With regards with [national declaration about Open Education in Morocco](#); this came as an outcome from the [Morocco](#) OE forum (December 2016), and it was

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built in a **participatory** manner, as it is inspired in the [Scottish Open Education Declaration](#), the text of the declaration and its improvement for discussion was widely documented and shared across the community towards ensuring that it was written in an **efficient** manner, to reach the largest possible number of endorsements to ensure that the declaration became **effective** in influencing the national policy. The model in which this declaration was designed can be considered **innovative**, as it was open for discussion prompting endorsements from world leading OE organisations and experts fostering a **coherent** argument between the discourse and the practice of openness, in order to ensure the transparency of the practices. All this process of open construction and discussions has been designed to make the declaration **relevant** for policy-makers in order to facilitate its adoption and endorsement.

5. The largest investment of the OpenMed projects are the [8 innovation Centres for Open Education](#) at South-Mediterranean partner universities where technical and networking infrastructure is available to university students, teachers and staff. The process of deciding which equipment to purchase and the reach of each centre was discussed in a **participatory** manner within each institution, while all the documentation was made available for all the partners during the selection and procurement of the equipment in order to ensure the **efficacy and effectiveness** of the implementation of the innovation centres. These centres aim at fostering **innovation** and capacity building towards engaging educators in creating OER in **coherence** with the main objectives of the project. The procurement of the equipment was designed to make clear the accountability of project towards ensuring the **transparency** of the purchases. The **relevance** of the centres design and equipment purchase was validated in order to ensure these could perform as expected according with the project objectives.
6. The biggest achievement of the OpenMed course are the 74 educators trained at the [Open Education Training Week in Torino](#) (September 2017) and [online](#) course (October 2017 – March 2018) to adopt Open Education approaches. The key element of this training is **participation**, as they course was co-created and openly valited for the community of practitioners, as all the partners took part in the project meetings and in the events related with the training development activities and the decisions were collectively agreed. With regards to the **documentation**, the course design methodology recorded all the actions and progress towards validating the content to ensure that all the learning activities were designed in an **efficient** manner towards ensuring the **effectiveness** of the learning activities, fostering **innovation** in professional development for

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curriculum design **coherently** with the principles and objectives of the project. The course design, including course content, materials, resources, were designed in a **transparent** way, so each one of the course stakeholders could contribute and provided feedback to ensure the quality of the resources, also, the process of revisions was held using an open-peer-review review approach by the external evaluator, who provided feedback and recommendations in an open and participative manner to ensure the **relevance** of the course content.

7. The [9 learning circles](#) in Egypt, Morocco, Palestine, Jordan and Lebanon facilitated by a network of 15 local facilitators are by far the most disruptive element of the project. The learning methodology has been widely **documented** in the research and conference papers presented in various journals and symposiums. The learning circles were designed to foster learning in an efficient and effective way, as participants co-created their learning by exchanging ideas ensuring the of the learning **efficacy and effectiveness** in a narrow time as the training was designed to maximise learning in than four months, using innovative methods and approaches fostering open learning in an holistic manner, towards equipping the learners with the skills needed not only to teach using OER and in adopting open educational practices, but in becoming trainers for other educators towards widening participation in the region, in **coherence** with the aims of the project. The learning circles also fostered **transparency**, as the participants exchanged and built practices that have been widely shared across the learners to ensure that the peer-review practices fostered **relevant** practices that can be further adopted and adapted according with each institutional needs.
8. In regards with [webinar series](#) on different aspects of Open Education, with international leaders in the field, these aimed at sharing with the partners and other stakeholders open educational practices and ideas with global leaders in Open Education and also, to present the OpenMed to these world leaders, in order to promote an arena to mutual exchange, fostering the **participation** of the partners in the global Open Education community. The **documentation** of the webinars are its recordings which are openly available in the project website as part of the [video collection](#). The webinars were designed to follow the activities of the modules in order to make these **efficient** and **effective**, by supporting their learning at different stages fostering elements to engaging the course participants in learning to develop **innovative** their projects providing the learners with a narrative **coherent** with the content provided in the modules from world leading researchers and advocates in order to enhance their learning. The webinars were held in a transparent manner, as these were

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publicly advertised through social media, publicly broadcasted and open to every interested participants outside of the OpenMed community and now these are openly available to be reused, adopted and adapted as are accessible in the OpenMed website. The webinars were very **relevant** to support the course activities, and, these were included as OER in the revised edition of the course in order to complement the materials designed for the course.

9. Regarding the variety of OER-related [projects](#) created by participants in the course, these are an outcome of the [9 learning circles](#). These were designed in a **participatory** manner, as co-creation and co-learning were fostered during the whole training course. The **documentation** of the participants' projects is openly available on a [site dedicated to disseminate the learners' outcomes](#), to ensure their **efficacy** and **effectiveness** as these are conceived to showcase good practices and ideas to inspire educators willing to Open Educational Practices towards fostering innovation in teaching and learning through OER as stated **coherently** with the project principles. In order to ensure that the projects were visible to the whole community, these were published in a **transparent** manner to make them accessible to the community of practice and to whoever may be looking for inspiration to create OER.
10. In relation with the training materials of the course "[Open Education: fundamentals and approaches](#)", composed by [5 modules](#), activities, and [project works](#) steps, publicly available in English, French, and Arabic, these have been designed in a **participatory** manner, first the themes and the content to design the syllabus was openly discussed, and later, each module as well as the whole course and its activities were agreed and validated in the facilitator's meeting held in [Madrid in May 2018](#). The **documentation** of the course and its evolution was clearly documented, as all the facilitators had access to all the files and could oversee the content while it was written, and also, the course final and amended materials have been made publicly available in the course [OpenMed website](#). To ensure the **efficiency** and **effectiveness** of the course materials, the materials were reviewed pre- and post course using an **innovative** assessment method known as open-peer-review, which was conducted in order make sure that resources, pedagogy, methodology and activities. In **coherence** with the open-peer-review methodology, the first course design [open-peer-review initial report](#) is openly available for the community and the post course and it was used to improve the content for the pilot. After the pilot, [another report](#) that gathered the perspective and evaluation of the course participants and the views from the external evaluator was shared across the community to enhance the content of the validated course, both reports are published in a

transparent way to ensure that all the stakeholders could access it and amend the content in order to make sure it was **relevant** for the learners and the community of practice.

11. A [Pilot Course Evaluation Report](#), with recommendations and suggestions for improving and enhancing future editions of the course follows the pilot of the course, was constructed in a **participatory** manner, as over 70 stakeholders were surveyed regarding the quality of the course and who also provided feedback to improve the course, both at content and practice level. This report follows up the [open-peer-review initial report](#), as the course content has been validated twice to ensure the quality of the course, both reports **document** this processes and are publicly available for consultation to ensure its **efficacy and effectiveness** of producing the expected results within the timeframe foreseen in working plan. The intention of the reports was to enhance the **innovative** methodology named [learning circles](#) developed for this project in **coherence** with the feedback provided by the community of practice to ensure that the content and activities are **relevant** to foster capacities across the partner institutions and also, across the MENA and Mediterranean region.
12. In regards the active network of experts and educators interested in promoting open education, this is an outcome of the 74 educators trained at the [Open Education Training Week in Torino](#) (September 2017), the [online](#) (October 2017 – March 2018) and of the [9 learning circles](#). This network has become a community of practice, which aims at broadening the **participation** of the members of the community in Open Education at institutional, national, regional and international level. Their activities are **documented** through a series of blogposts, conference and research articles papers, reports, presentations and news which are publicly available in the [publications sections](#) of the OpenMed website. active network of experts and educators aims at fostering open education in an **efficient** and **effective** way, by inspiring others and promoting good practices and **innovation** within their institutions and across the region, in soundness and **coherence** with the OpenMed project. The OpenMed community of practice has fostered a series of **transparent** procedures, including the [OER Regional Agenda for the South-Mediterranean Universities](#) and its [revision and discussion](#), alongside with [national declaration about Open Education in Morocco](#), the [Pilot Course Evaluation Report](#) to enhance the course content and practices and the procurement of the equipment for the [8 innovation Centres for Open Education](#) in order to ensure the **relevance** of their activities, involving them in across different stages of the project.

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13. Finally, the [set of recommendations](#) to institutional leaders and policy makers to strategically prioritise Open Education to further develop the education system in the South-Mediterranean were designed in a **participatory** manner, as many stakeholders contributed to these guidelines. The **documentation** of the recommendations has been made available to the partners to be discussed to make sure that the guidelines were both **effective** and **efficient** to foster the development of institutional policies. The aim of these recommendations is to foster **innovation** through the [8 innovation Centres for Open Education](#) at the premises of partner universities, towards facilitating the development of institutional roadmaps and action plans for the implementation of open education at local and institutional levels, in coherence with the project objectives. The nature of these recommendations is **transparent**, fostering co-creation of policies in which all the voices are heard and acknowledged, to ensure that the fostered policies are relevant to only to senior management, but also to educators, learners, instructional designers, researchers and other members of the educational community.

III. Unexpected outcomes/ spin-off effects

During the project, two unexpected but highly important outcomes have been developed, and both aim at supporting the OpenMed community continuing fostering Open Educational Practices and Open Education Policies in the long run, adding value to the project from the policy and practice perspective.

1. [National declaration about Open Education in Morocco](#): The idea of launching a national declaration was coined during the [Morocco Open Education Day at Cadi Ayyad University on December](#), where a large series of projects and initiatives from Moroccan universities were showcased, including OERs and massive open online courses (MOOCs). During the discussion at the forum, Moroccan educators agreed that the creation, use and sharing of OER can help to address the challenges HEIs faced in the country, this conversation led the discussion towards developing a National Declaration to further support, enhance and develop Open Educational Resources and practices, following the example of Scotland and its [Scottish Open Education Declaration](#) , the [Cape Town Open Education Declaration](#) and [the Paris OER Declaration](#).
2. [UNIMED sub-network on eLearning and Open Education](#): This network aims at contributing to and support UNIMED members in their efforts to further

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enhance and promote innovation in teaching and learning by engaging with university departments, academics, researchers, librarians, practitioners and learning technologists, fostering developments in e-learning infrastructure, e-learning methodology and pedagogy, blended learning, innovation policies and strategies, online learning environments and tools, learning analytics, improvement of learning experience, Open Educational Resources, MOOCs, digital literacy, game-based learning, virtual classrooms and laboratories and virtual exchange.

As reported on the UNIMED website, the main objectives of the Sub-network are:

- To gather and share information directly from the main actors in the sector in the whole Mediterranean region in order to create new networks and partnerships and develop joint projects;
- To collaboratively carry out studies, analysis and research papers on the issue,
- To organise international events (workshops, seminars, and conferences, webinars, trainings, summer schools) to improve the flow of knowledge and exchanging experiences between researchers and scholars;
- To build capacity of faculty and managerial staff to use eLearning and Open Education approaches, through online courses and through a series of seminars for university professors members of the Sub-network.
- To support the development and implementation of eLearning and Open Education institutional policies within its members.

IV. Recommendations for future activities

The recommendations listed in this report aim at supporting the OpenMed partners and other stakeholders in sustaining the activities in which they have committed to foster beyond the end of the project. These recommendations are divided in two groups, 1) promoting the development of capacities in Open Education, and 2) in fostering sustainable Open Education policies, aiming at providing guidelines to educators, senior management and policy-makers in order to further promote the use of the outcomes of the project.

To build capacities in Open Education, the recommendations address the future of [8 Innovation Centres for Open Education](#) for the creation of OER, and to build capacities by fostering the reuse of methodologies delivered at the [Open Education Training Week in Torino](#) alongside with the adoption of [Open Education: fundamentals and](#)

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[approaches](#) course and the [learning circles](#) and the OER-related [projects](#) created by the participants in the course.

To develop sustainable Open Education Policies, the recommendation will address the following the adoption of the [OER Regional Agenda for the South-Mediterranean Universities](#), the continuation of the [OER National Strategy Forums](#), and the [set of recommendations](#) to institutional leaders and policy makers to strategically prioritise Open Education.

1. Recommendations to foster capacity building

To develop capacities to educators in the MENA region, the legacy of OpenMed results can reach a large number of educators and can support institutions in developing OER to support their learners.

To achieve this aim, the OpenMed partners are recommended to:

- To take advantage of the [8 innovation Centres for Open Education](#), it is recommended that these are maintained to become hubs for content production, and to train faculty and learning technologists, but also, fostering the development of good practices, and document them to foster scholarly research.
- Following the practices and methodologies used in the [Open Education Training Week in Torino](#), it is recommended to foster face to face learning and to document and share the practices and resources developed for such trainings, as well as recording the speakers, to build on the resources that can be used to train educators both face to face and online.
- To further promote the adoption, reuse, adaptation, localisation and contextualisation, it is recommended that the training materials of the course [Open Education: fundamentals and approaches](#) which are available English, French, and Arabic are uploaded by each partner in their own learning management system, and to enable recognition and accreditation mechanisms to validate the academic development of the learners. Also, is important to ensure that the recognition mechanisms, such as certificates or diplomas are valid as a proof of learning for external participants from other institutions, which may also be interested in registering in the course, as these can foster regional leadership in capacity building for the partner universities. In order to ensure that the content is available to be adopted by the partner universities, it is necessary to ensure that the packages provided to the stakeholders have all

the content well structured and that the links and media files are fully functional as it now in the [validated version of the course](#).

- The [learning circles](#) as are an innovative methodology fostered by the project, and its practicality in foster peer-learning and knowledge co-creation can be acknowledged by fostering learning circles as a good way to build communities of practice inside and outside the institutions, as the members of the learning circles that successfully complete the course can be included as facilitators or mentors to support others who may be willing to adopt Open Educational Practices and to create OER.
- Finally, its is recommended to continue fostering OER-related [projects](#) created by participants in the courses, as these are great ways to recognise learning and learners and to inspire good practices from early career practitioners.

2. Recommendations to foster Open Education policies

- In relation with the [OER Regional Agenda for the South-Mediterranean Universities](#), it is recommended to adopt it, so start shaping institutional action plans and roadmaps at institutional level, considering the key elements that the agenda addresses, such as fostering mechanisms for enhancing students access to Higher Education, promote improvement of quality of teaching and learning practices, support participant universities to widen participation in Open Education, raise awareness on the benefits of OER use, reuse and remix for university course development and support the collaboration among universities on issues related to Open Education, considering its five key strategic areas Open Content and Licenses, Open Pedagogy and Practice, Technology, Governance and business models, collaborative models between institutions, as all these domains and areas can support innovation and foster Open Education policies.
- The [OER National Strategy Forums](#) are key to engage senior management, representatives of the government an practitioners in a shared arena to discuss and exchange experiences and expertise in order to enable policy or strategic developments in which the practitioners voices are acknowledged, as these are the key enablers when a policy or strategy, needs to be implemented, in order to prevent reluctance or mistrust from faculty, as when academics are included in decision-making processes they tend to be more prone to adopt new practices or approaches.

- Finally, it is recommended to adopt the [set of recommendations](#) to institutional leaders and policy makers to strategically prioritise Open Education to further develop the education system in the South-Mediterranean. As part of this, the following domains are suggested to be addressed in an institutional policies are: **Support democratic and diverse access to knowledge**, as Open Education is about human rights, Institutional leaders should ensure that all educational materials produced by public institutions and developed with public funds are openly available; **Build Capacities in Open Education**, as when a critical mass of impactful activities are visible, a long lasting cultural change can occur within the institutions involved, so it is key to incorporate openness training programmes, enhancing capacity on the use and value of Open Educational Practices; **Instil a Culture of Openness by rewarding Open Education**, as Open Education represents a culture of openness, transparency, trust and collaboration within and outside institutions, fostering international cooperation between education stakeholders to maximise educational investments and to develop a global pool of culturally diverse, locally relevant, gender-sensitive, accessible, educational materials in multiple languages and formats, and finally, **direct human capital and economic resources towards Open Education initiatives**, as Openness in Higher Education can stimulate the supply and demand for high-quality OERs which are essential for modernising education. If universities want to find more resources to invest in better teaching and research, it is essential that the open sharing of resources is encouraged.

In general, Open Educational Policies should be designed to inspire and interact with other institutional policies, adapt and influence technological developments, consider more evidence than data, regard copyright and its reforms, connect with the openness ecosystems, consider learning accreditation through Open Education and be attentive to context. Therefore, when designing Open Education Policies, it is recommended that the following elements are considered, as these can act as catalysts and enablers if correctly acknowledged and included or become barriers and challenges if disregarded or poorly addressed:

1. **Process and Partners** - When designing a policy in a novel subject such as Open Education, and in order to prevent misunderstandings and frictions inside a University, it is important the involvement of others in co-designing the policy, such as librarians, stakeholders from e-learning and digital education departments, as well as ICT staff and heads of departments and pedagogical units, but also, educators and researchers, as these will be directly affected by the policy. Also, it is

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recommended to involve experts in Open Education from other countries that can advise in the policy making process.

2. **Context** - Also, when designing a policy in Open Education, stakeholders need to be aware of the socio-cultural issues at play and review similar policies in order to establish a process of international policy bench learning.
3. **Stakeholders** - To foster sustainable Open Education Policies, some key people are needed to develop it, such as educational policy experts, senior management from the pedagogical units and from the libraries, also copyright advisors should be included alongside with heads of departments, but it is also important to include educators in every stage of the process, as these should be leading on the implementation of the policy, communicating its value to the rest of the faculty and to the students.
4. **Solutions and approaches** - In order to ensure the successful development and implementation of the policy, stakeholders need to carefully review other policies addressing education at institution and country level, alongside with education regulatory models (laws, decrees or directives) in order to ensure that the policy can be effectively implemented. Also, it is key to consider technical or third party solutions, as OERs are enabled by technology, therefore, the software and hardware adopted to produce resources need to be carefully evaluated, as well as the repositories in which the resources will be archived, which can be installed in the institution itself or provided by external organisations.
5. **Policy opportunities** - When designing a policy, it is key to identify the opportunities it can provide for individuals, communities, and institutions, as these opportunities are the key enablers to engage with the educators and learners during the implementation and rolling out stages.
6. **Policy challenges** - Also, it is key to identify the specific challenges or barriers that the policy may face, to find mitigating strategies to prevent unnecessary obstructions.
7. **Key Elements** - It is recommended that policy-makers review other core elements to support their policy, both at design and implementation

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level, as for example, international experiences and experts, can support the uptake of the policy.

8. **Evidence** - In order key design a policy, certain amount of evidence to validate the claims and to showcase gaps and needs, therefore the information and data used in the policies needs to be carefully selected. The evidence needed to foster a policy are international and national reports, scholarly literature, reviews of good practices, and also, quantitative information about the education state of the arts in a country or region and its educational needs and challenges, and also, data about financial savings or revenues that can be obtained needs to be portrayed in the policy.
9. **Beneficiaries** - Educational Policies must be designed to benefit communities of people and to enhance and improve education, therefore the people that will benefit from the policy needs to be clearly addressed, and they need to be aware of how this policy aims at helping them and supporting their activities, in order to engage them efficiently during the implementation process.
10. **Risks** - Finally, and in order to ensure the sustainability of the policy in the mid and long term, the risks that the policy may face need to be accounted in the design process, some risks can be the change of management and governance, copyright reforms and also educational systems reforms, in order to have guarantees and mitigation processed in order to prevent affecting the beneficiaries as much as possible.